

ივანე ჯავახიშვილის სახელობის თბილისის სახელმწიფო უნივერსიტეტი
ეკონომიკისა და ბიზნესის ფაკულტეტი

უნივერსიტეტის დაარსებისა და ეკონომიკისა და ბიზნესის ფაკულტეტის
100 წლის იუბილესადმი მიძღვნილი საერთაშორისო სამეცნიერო კონფერენცია

„კოვიდ 19 პანდემია და ეკონომიკა“

Ivane Javakhishvili Tbilisi State University
Faculty of Economics and Business

International Scientific Conference Dedicated to the Establishment of the
University and the 100th Anniversary of the Faculty of Economics and Business

“Covid 19 Pandemic and Economics”

8 თებერვალი, 2022 / 8 February, 2022
თბილისი / Tbilisi

Value Choices of the Community in the Context of the Covid-19 Pandemic

Shota Veshapidze

*Associate Professor
Ivane Javakhishvili Tbilisi State University*

Gia Zoidze

*Invited Lecturer
Batumi State University*

As a result of the global Covid-19 pandemic, the Georgian economy found itself in crisis. The pandemic also threatens the traditions and values of the community. The country needs to overcome the negative consequences caused by the pandemic, which has acquired a global character. Great global changes are taking place in the world. Just as the epoch-making transformations that began in the 1960s laid the groundwork for what is happening today, further changes will be driven by the consequences of overcoming COVID-19. This applies to everything, including values. Today world processes offer a new challenge to everyone. In order for the demands of globalization to be met and for the country to find its place and function in the modern world, a state thinking based on human values is necessary. The existence of a state-minded society is an irreversible guarantee of progress.

Keywords: Value orientations of the economy, unity, freedom, reforms, progress.

In order to determine how to act, how to find alternatives available in all aspects of human life, we need to understand where we need to go, what we want. That's it, first of all, we have to choose the main value orientations. Sociologists define values as the opinion formed in society, the attitudes about what is important and insignificant, right and wrong. Therefore, values are what society considers most important, right and wrong. (Charkviani, 2019)

It is important for our era to consider current events and processes in relativity. The peculiarity of such an approach is that everything is viewed in terms of its country, its place (geostrategic situation), environmental conditions and historical situation (in terms of time), depending on them. Such an approach presents economic life not as an understanding of events but as a relation (explanation). Based on the establishment of such a ratio, it is possible to establish relationships that are acceptable to the whole society. Such is the universal method of achieving the optimal synthesis of universal and national values, of achieving a unified progress through the preservation of our "Ego", "local trifles", traditions and customs.

All of the above, in the conditions of modern globalization, have an invaluable, practical purpose for each country. Georgia has rich traditions in this direction. In Georgian economic thought, education was considered to be the most important for the country's progress. This is considered to be the main basis for the success of David Aghmashenebeli and Queen Tamar Khan's Georgia. (Chavchavadze, 1997, 2007). The principles and core values, the implementation of which can lead to progress, are still relevant today. Among these principles are: unity, striving for freedom, reconstruction, reforms and progress.

On the hierarchical scale of values, the highest value is the person. To save and protect their lives, people are creating a state. The state seeks to ensure the physical security of people from external and internal threats. Its function is also to protect justice in the lives of citizens. The social development of any country, including the economic one, is related to the state.

From the 90s of the last century, when the Internet took over the world, a new era began. In the field of technology, in the modern world, amazing progress has already been made, although there have

been many serious challenges, which make us think that we will all either improve life as a whole, part of the common space of the earth, or face insurmountable obstacles. The solution, of course, exists, and it is, in our opinion, only one: the main focus should be shifted by everyone to the human being, and everything should be done to bring to the forefront the core human values, such as: the right to life, liberty and the pursuit of happiness.

In our time, many life-threatening calamities have been revealed. Their list is quite a long list: Dividing people into ours and others; Ethnic-racial and religious arrogance and arrogance; Indifference towards poor and destitute people; Using pietist discourse for political manipulation; Critical and irrational support for the legitimation of religion by political and economic elites; Discrimination against women and the neglect of the feminist perspective in life and politics; Violence justified in the name of religion and God; Persecution and harassment of religious minorities. To see a national threat in their existence. Demonizing and persecuting LGBTQ + people. To use the Judeo-Christian and Islamic scriptures for this, even though they do not say anything about the phenomenon of different sexual orientations; Careless treatment of the ecosystem. Its exploitation and destruction; Carelessness, cruelty and consumerism towards domestic and wild animals-birds. Who cares, how many more things we have to replace society with love, joy, peace and kindness. (Songhulashvili, 2022)

To the above, now the global Covid-19 pandemic has also been added. We are losing dozens of people every day in Georgia, as of February 1, 2022, more than 13,000 people have already died in the Covid-Pandemic. It does not seem like we are all doing our best to save each person's life. People do not trust vaccination, do not trust the government that organizes the vaccination process.

Trust is the most important component of an ethical life, as it affects all areas of public life: personal, social, religious, and business relationships. Nothing breaks the constraint of the state together like a reduction and loss of trust. The principle of justice requires us to recognize that the state can use its position either for universal good (for social reforms, for the establishment of a just society), or for its own interests (for political and economic power). We have examples of one in history as well as another. (Songhulashvili, 2022)

In the nineteenth century, criticism of religion emerged within the framework of political-economic discourse. But, social issues are still unresolved today. Georgia is facing many challenges. Among them are the creation of new jobs, employment of young and old, assistance to the socially vulnerable, water supply to villages, improvement of transport and logistics services, creation of new municipal transport in the regions. It must also continue to rehabilitate pandemic-affected households and small businesses, address housing problems, and further development of infrastructure.

In the era of globalization, one of the main values is the formation of state thinking. Such thinking attaches great importance to the service of the land with true faith, dignity, freedom, and responsibility. It is also important to distinguish between ideological extremes and to understand the superiority of "our" need over "me" and "my" needs. Today, world processes offer a new challenge to everyone, Our nation must also respond to the demands offered by globalization and find its place and function in the modern world, which inevitably requires the formation of state thinking. The existence of a state-minded society is an irreversible benchmark for progress.

An important guideline of state thinking should be the rational solution of the socio-economic problems of the society. This state thinking should include an in-depth and comprehensive analysis in

terms of political, socio-economic, technological, legal, environmental, ethical and demographic factors. First of all, the country needs peace, stability, predictability. It is also necessary to employ the population, to develop small and medium-sized businesses, to revive agriculture, to fill our market with local products. It is necessary to promote science, culture and sports and, naturally, to take care of the restoration of the country's integrity. There is no single sector that can bring the country out of the crisis alone. Appropriate projects need to be implemented in the areas of infrastructure, economy, local production, agriculture, education, health, sports, culture. In order to preserve Georgia's identity in the era of globalization, the main condition is to create a Georgian state based on modern technologies and achievements based on our traditions. (Catholicos-Patriarch of All Georgia Ilia II, 2006, 2009)

Now, we need not undermine the foundation necessary for the establishment of any free and progressive state. Above all, it is freedom, dignity, peace, stability of the country, respect for human rights, protection of property, freedom of business, free media, strong civil society. We must use our resources in the international division of labor. The most important resource for humanity is water. In the long run, the importance of fresh water will increase especially, the consumption of which is increasing rapidly in the world. Increased demand for water supply requires the development of new technologies for its treatment, protection (storage) and transportation. Georgia is one of the big owners of water resources, so in the future we must find our place in the world water market. Today, the development of agriculture, small and medium business should become a top priority. Jobs must be created so that people can be employed and get out of difficult social conditions. (Catholicos-Patriarch of All Georgia Ilia II, 2022, 2009, 2006, 2005)

Our great resource is intellectual potential as well. In the post-polar economy, the role of intellectual resources is steadily growing, and the struggle to obtain them is intensifying. The country should not lose the scientific achievements it has. We must make full use of even the scientific or economic achievements of the Soviet period, much of which we have almost completely given up and lost. As for science, it must be said that Georgia has world-renowned researchers in many fields. In general, the scientific field plays a crucial role in the development of any country, its formation requires a lot of money and a lot of time. The country must use its rich scientific potential.

Conclusions

The Covid-19 pandemic has posed new challenges for Georgia. The country's economy has experienced a deep crisis. In addition, the preliminary results of 2021 show that the crisis will be overcome. New opportunities and areas have emerged. The crisis was followed by the proliferation of remote services, a very rapid growth in the pharmaceutical field. The fields of technological and artificial intelligence have become more important, and reasonable cooperation between the state and the private sector has been further enhanced. The balance between the center and the regions has changed, nature, ecology, the village has acquired a new destination. Our hospitality traditions shaken by the pandemic have been revived. Overcoming the negative consequences caused by the pandemic should lead to a rapid recovery of the economy and the acceleration of development.

First of all, it is necessary to effectively implement measures to prevent the spread of coronavirus by providing a flexible health care system. In line with it, the competitiveness of the manufacturing, agriculture and tourism sectors must be increased in order for the country to be attractive for investment.

It is important to raise the entrepreneurial culture, improve access to finance, implement programs adapted to the regional and cultural peculiarities of Georgia. European standards must be adopted quickly, Georgian legislation must be harmonized with EU legislation. Promoting internationalization, electronic communications, information technology, innovation, research and development is an important priority.

In terms of economic growth of the country, it is important to improve infrastructure, macroeconomic stability, labor market dynamics, financial system stability. An important way to tackle economic growth and unemployment is to increase state support for companies through the implementation of various programs, ensuring universal access to monetary resources, and liberalization of the tax system. The government can create a competitive environment, develop basic infrastructure, take care of education, make it easier to do business, introduce low, reasonable taxes, reduce business loans, reduce interest rates.

It is important that companies, start-ups, are closely acquainted with the requirements of the DCFTA of the Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Agreement with the European Union. This will make it possible to see how the agreement provides opportunities, what are the requirements in terms of goods and their quality in the EU market. Georgian products are often not competitive in the EU market in terms of price and quality. It is important to know how businesses work together in the EU. This will enable entrepreneurs to overcome low productivity, low access to knowledge and technology. It is also important for entrepreneurs to realize that it is necessary to increase the quality of products, to disseminate relevant information about products in the EU and other markets.

References:

1. Charkviani, G. (2019). "Globalization", salon conversations. The Thinking Academy. Available at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=j7lmwx-VJto&t=6s> (accessed: 04.02.2022)
2. Chavchavadze, I. (1997). Domestic review. Complete collection of works in twenty volumes, Vol. VI, "Ilia Foundation", Tbilisi.
3. Chavchavadze, I. (2007). Equality of ranks. Complete collection of works in twenty volumes, Volume X. "Ilia Foundation". P. 371-373.
4. Gvelesiani, M., & Veshapidze, S. (2016). European Values: What Can We Implement from Them and How Can We Implement Them in Georgia. *Globalization & Business*.
5. Papava, V. (2020). Coronomic crisis: When the economy is a hostage to medicine. *Eurasia Review*.
6. Papava, V. (2020). On the COVID-19 pandemic economic crisis and the reorientation of the Georgian economy. *Reflecting on a Changed World*.
7. Sichinava, A., Chikava, M., Veshapidze, S., Sekhniashvili, D., & Pailodze, N. (2013). [Realities of internationalization of higher education in Georgia](#).
8. Silagadze, A., Zubiashvili, T., (2016). [Georgia's economy against the background of the associate agreement with the European Union](#). *International Journal of Business and Management Studies* 5 (2), 533-540.
9. Silagadze, A. (2008). Origin of Liberal Economic Doctrines". *Innovation*", Tbilisi.
10. Songhulashvili M. (2022). Subversive prayer - Christmas address of the Metropolitan of Tbilisi. Available at: <https://tabula.ge/ge/news/678082-dzircamomtkhrelilotsva-tbileli-mitropolitistfbclid=IwAR0ki2CxAXpsP0Q1KkSKA7DY6orZT3N2uw5xFlSPxWprIJ3V3pdMATCANjI> (accessed: 04.02.2022)
11. Tvalchrelidze, A. G., & Silagadze, A. (2020). Influence of COVID-19 coronavirus pandemic on international oil markets.- *Zeszyty Naukowe Akademii Morskiej w Szczecinie*.
12. Veshapidze, S., & Zoidze, G., & Berishvili K. (2021). THE ECONOMIC DETERMINANT OF THE EDUCATION SYSTEM. *Sciences of Europe*, (81-2), 6-12.
DOI: 10.24412/3162-2364-2021-81-2-6-12

13. Veshapidze, S., CHIABRISHVILI, K., Zubiashvili, T., & Zoidze, G. (2021). ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EDUCATION AND ECONOMIC SECURITY. *Ecoforum Journal*, 10(3).
14. Veshapidze, S., & Zoidze, G. (2021). Institutional Evolution of Higher Education in Georgia. *The New Economist*, 16(2), 1-1.
DOI: 10.36962/NEC6102202133
15. Veshapidze, S., Zoidze, G. (2022). On State Intervention in the Economy through the Budget in Georgia. *WORLD ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL ECONOMIC RELATIONS. - International Scientific Collection - Vol. 5*. Kyiv – CUL.
16. Veshapidze, S., Zubiashvili, T., (2020). About the Origins of Modern Geoeconomic Foundations of Georgia. *Ecoforum Journal* 9 (2).
17. Veshapidze, S., & Zubiashvili, T. (2021). About population growth and global problems.
18. Veshapidze, S., (2019). Structure of European value system. *World economy and international economic relations*.
19. Veshapidze, S., (2020). [Religion and national values in Georgia](#). *International Scientific Collection*, Volume 3, pp. 33-36.
20. Veshapidze, S., (2017). [THE TRADITIONS ORIENTATED ON EUROPEAN VALUES IN GEORGIA](#). *Sciences of Europe*. VOL 4, No 13 (13)
21. Veshapidze, S., Darbaidze, M., Beridze, T., (2016). [Euro-Atlantic values: what tie up us](#). Universal. pp. 230-235.
22. Veshapidze, S., Babuadze, N., & Beridze, T. (2015). EUROPEAN VALUES AND CHOICE OF GEORGIA (HUMAN DIGNITY, LAWFUL SOVEREIGNTY, DEMOCRACY AND WELLBEING). *ACTUAL PROBLEMS OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF NATIONAL ECONOMIES.(10-11 July, 2015)*. PUBLISHING HOUSE OF PAATA GUGUSHVILI INSTITUTE OF ECONOMICS OF IVANE JAVAKHISHVILI TBILISI STATE UNIVERSITY. Tbilisi, 79-83.
23. Zoidze, G. (2021). Basic Paradigms of Institutional Economics. *Publishing House "Universal*, 202.
DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.5544934](#)
24. Zoidze, G. (2021). Importance of Euro-Atlantic Integration: Democracy, Security and Economic Development. *Three Seas Economic Journal*, 2(3), 1-7.
25. Zoidze, G., & Abuselidze, G. (2021). COVID-19 pandemic and currency risk analysis in Georgia. *Entrepreneurship*, 9 (2), 33-46
DOI:10.37708/ep.swu.v9i2.3
26. Zoidze, G. (2020). GEORGIAN AGRO-SPHERE DEVELOPMENT PRIORITIES AND WAYS OF CARRYING OUT SOME IMPROVEMENTS. *Mysl Ekonomiczna i Polityczna*, (2 (69)), 55-71.
DOI: 10.26399/meip.2(69).2020.10/g.zoidze
27. Zoidze, G., & Tkhilaishvili, G. (2021). Prospects of Intermodal Transportation and Logistics Channels Development for Georgia. In *Proceedings of 25th International Scientific Conference. Transport Means*
28. Zoidze, G. (2020). Risks Caused by Pandemics and Anti-crisis Management. Ivane Javakhishvili Tbilisi State University, Paata Gugushvili Institute of Economics. In *Proceedings of Materials of International Scientific Conference Dedicated to the 115th Birth Anniversary of Academician Paata Gugushvili* (pp. 190-195).
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5544942
29. Zubiashvili, T., & Zubiashvili, N. (2021). POPULATION AGING–A GLOBAL CHALLENGE. *Ecoforum Journal*, 10(2).
30. Christmas Epistle of the Catholicos-Patriarch of All Georgia Ilia II (January 7). 2022. „Formula News“. Available at: <https://formulanews.ge/News/62705> (accessed: 04.02.2022)
31. Easter Epistle of the Catholicos-Patriarch of All Georgia Ilia II (May 2-8). 2005. "Kviris Palitra".
32. Easter Epistle of the Catholicos-Patriarch of All Georgia Ilia II (April 24 - 30). 2006. "Kviris Palitra".
33. Easter Epistle of the Catholicos-Patriarch of All Georgia Ilia II (April 20 - 26). 2009. "Kviris Palitra".
34. The Catholicos-Patriarch of All Georgia Ilia II. 2004. Speech at the International Forum on Globalization and the Dialogue of Civilizations, Sheraton-Metechi Palace, "Patriarchate Agencies", # 38.

საზოგადოების ღირებულებითი არჩევანი კოვიდ-19 პანდემიის პირობებში

შოთა ვეშაპიძე

ასოცირებული პროფესორი
ივანე ჯავახიშვილის სახელობის თბილისის სახელმწიფო უნივერსიტეტი

გია ზოიძე

მოწვეული ლექტორი
ბათუმის სახელმწიფო უნივერსიტეტი

ანოტაცია

გლობალური Covid-19-ის პანდემიის შედეგად საქართველოს ეკონომიკა კრიზისში აღმოჩნდა. პანდემია საფრთხეს უქმნის საზოგადოების ტრადიციებსა და ღირებულებებს. ქვეყანამ უნდა დაძლიოს პანდემიით გამოწვეული უარყოფითი შედეგები, რომელმაც გლობალური ხასიათი შეიძინა. მსოფლიოში დიდი გლობალური ცვლილებები ხდება. ისევე, როგორც 1960-იან წლებში დაწყებულმა ეპოქალურმა გარდაქმნებმა საფუძველი ჩაუყარა იმას, რაც დღეს ხდება, შემდგომი ცვლილებები განპირობებული იქნება COVID-19-ის დაძლევის შედეგებით. ეს ეხება ყველა საკითხს ღირებულებების ჩათვლით. იმისათვის, რომ გლობალიზაციის მოთხოვნები დაკმაყოფილდეს და ქვეყანამ იპოვოს თავისი ადგილი და ფუნქცია თანამედროვე სამყაროში, საჭიროა ადამიანურ ღირებულებებზე დაფუძნებული სახელმწიფოებრივი აზროვნება. სახელმწიფოებრივად მოაზროვნე საზოგადოების არსებობა პროგრესის შეუქცევადი გარანტიაა.

საკვანძო სიტყვები: ეკონომიკის ღირებულებითი ორიენტაციები, ერთიანობა, თავისუფლება, რეფორმები, პროგრესი.